

A Study of Student Satisfaction of the Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University Radio Station

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Abstract—The research aimed to study the satisfaction of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University students towards the university radio station which broadcasts in both analog on FM 97.25 MHz and online via the university website. The sample used in this study consists of undergraduate students year 1 to year 4 from 6 faculties i.e. Faculty of Education, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Faculty of Management Science and Faculty of Industrial Technology, and Faculty of Fine and Applied Arts totaling 200 students. The tools used for data collection is survey. Data analysis applied statistics that are percentage, mean and standard deviation. The results showed that Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University students were satisfied to the place of listening service, followed by channels of broadcasting that cover both analog signals on 97.25 MHz FM and online via the Internet. However, the satisfaction level of the content offered was very low. Most of the students want the station to improve the content. Entertainment content was requested the most, followed by sports content. The lowest satisfaction level is with the broadcasting quality through analog signal. Most students asked the station to improve on the issue. However, overall, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University students were satisfied with the university radio station broadcasted online via the university website.

Keywords—Satisfaction, students, radio station, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University.

I. INTRODUCTION

PRESENTLY, information is much more important to people's daily lives. People who are very much exposed to the information will have advantage over their business competitors. Therefore, information dissemination channels have been developed to highly increase its effectiveness. Communication technology has also been developed, so that information disseminated in the past with limitation can now be done widely in public [1]. All societies need quick, accurate, and adequate information to be used for their own organizational development, in terms of social, business, politics, entertainment, and especially education. Development of information technology to digital age helps disseminate data of all countries and languages to the world in such a short time. People can receive information all the time, and in many more different forms. Text, picture and sound can also be disseminated in much higher quality than in the past [2], [3].

Thailand is one of the countries that needs to adapt itself to be competitive with other countries in the world. In B.E. 2559 (2016), Thailand will join the Asian Economic Community (AEC) in which Thailand must prepare and develop itself to be more competitive with the global community, and need

information for development in every aspect. National Broadcasting and Telecommunications Commission (NBTC) has been set up to supervise information dissemination to people in Thailand, which leads to the development of information dissemination channels in every aspect, including broadcasting business, television business, and telecommunication business. Frequency allocation has also been done for both public and private sectors.

Radio broadcast is one of the communication channels which has been developed in communication technology continuously. NBTC authorizes frequency allocation to both public and private sectors to be used for the dissemination of data, information, according to the organization's objectives.

Presently, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University is developing the quality of education into international standard to prepare for AEC. Therefore, the University has developed communication channels to facilitate the society, especially the University students, in accessing academic and general information. The University's radio broadcast station FM 97.25 MHz, broadcasted in both analog on FM 97.25 MHz and online via the University website, is another channel to offer information and social mobility, and also to entertain students outside class. A study of students' satisfaction; therefore, reflects the quality of listening service of data, information and entertainment, the quality of the University radio broadcast station's contents, and a channel of listening to the broadcast from the radio station, for further service and content improvement in accordance with students' need in the future.

Fig. 1 Radio Production 1

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II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- A. To study students' satisfaction towards listening the program of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University radio broadcast station.
- B. To create an improvement guideline for listening service and contents of radio broadcast program in accordance with students' need.

III. SCOPE OF THE STUDY AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study relies on survey research, using 2 approaches which are documentary research and field study with questionnaire as a tool for data collection from sample group. Details are as follows.

- A. Population used in this research is first year to fourth year undergraduate students of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. Sample group used in this research is first year to fourth year undergraduate students of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University of 200 students, using calculation formula of sample group. The research selects sample group by systematic random sampling. [4]
- B. The tool used to collect data was a questionnaire of the satisfaction of university students on the Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University Radio Station.

- College Year: The vast majority of respondents 61 (30.5%) are in the third college year, followed by the second year students 58 (29.0%).
- Faculty: Most respondents, 49 (24.5%) are from Faculty of Management, followed by 46 (23.0%) from Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences.

TABLE I
NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF RESPONDENTS' GENERAL INFORMATION

General information	Number	%	
1. Gender	Male	72	36.0
	Female	128	64.0
2. Age	17-20	112	56.0
	21-24	68	34.0
	Over 25	20	10.0
3. College Year	1 st Year	46	23.0
	2 nd Year	58	19.0
	3 rd Year	61	30.5
	4 th Year	31	15.5
	Over 4 th Year	4	2.0
4. Faculty	Education	28	14.0
	Humanities and Social Sciences	46	23.0
	Science and Technology	32	16.0
	Management Science	49	24.5
	Fine Arts	25	12.5
	Industrial Technology	20	10.0
Total	200	100.0	

TABLE II
NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF THE SAMPLE GROUP CATEGORIZED BY THE LISTENING FREQUENCY TO GENERAL RADIO STATION

Listening frequency per week	Number	%
1. Every day	18	9.0
2. 5-6 days	22	11.0
3. 3-4 days	72	36.0
4. 1-2 days	88	44.0
Total	200	100.0

Table II shows that most of the students 88 (44.0%) listen to general radio station 1-2 days a week, followed by 72 (36.0%) which have listening frequency of 3-4 days a week. 18 (9.0%) are in daily listening frequency group which is the least proportion.

TABLE III
NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF THE SAMPLE GROUP CATEGORIZED BY THE LENGTH OF LISTENING HOUR PER DAY

Listening hour per day	Number	%
1. More than 5 hours	24	12.0
2. 3-4 hours	32	16.0
3. 1-2 hours	48	24.0
4. Less than 1 hour	96	48.0
Total	200	100.0

Table III showing that the highest number of respondents 96 (48.0%) spend less than 1 hour a day listening to the radio, followed by 48 (24.0%) are in the listening length of 1-2 hours a day range. 24 (12.0%) are in the least group that spend over 5 listening hours a day.

Table IV showing that on weekday most of the students 32 (16%) have listening period at 6.01-8.00 pm., followed by the period of 10.01-12.00 am., which have 28 (14%) respondents.

Fig. 2 Radio Production 2

IV. DATA COLLECTION

Part A. General Information

The analysis of general information of the respondents – gender, age, College year of study, faculty and general behavior of radio listening are presented in Tables I-V.

Table I shows research findings from personal data analysis of questionnaire from 200 respondents, showing general information categorized by sex, age, college year and faculty, as follows:

- Gender: The majority, 128 of the respondents, are female which cover 64.0% of the total group and 72 (36%) are male.
- Age: It is founded that most respondents 112 (56.0%) fall in the 17-20-year age range, followed by 68 (34.0%) are in 21-24 year range.

TABLE IV
NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF THE SAMPLE GROUP CATEGORIZED BY PERIOD OF LISTENING TO RADIO ON WEEK DAY (MONDAY - FRIDAY)

Listening period	Number	%
1. 00.01-02.00 am	12	6.0
2. 02.01-04.00 am	6	3.0
3. 04.01-06.00 am	2	1.0
4. 06.01-08.00 am	14	7.0
5. 08.01-10.00 am	22	11.0
6. 10.01-12.00 am	28	14.0
7. 00.01-02.00 pm	14	7.0
8. 02.01-04.00 pm	8	4.0
9. 04.01-06.00 pm	18	9.0
10. 06.01-08.00 pm	32	16.0
11. 08.01-10.00 pm	22	11.0
12. 10.01-12.00 pm	22	11.0
Total	200	100.0

TABLE V
NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF THE SAMPLE GROUP CATEGORIZED BY PERIOD OF LISTENING TO RADIO ON SATURDAY AND SUNDAY

Listening period	Number	%
1. 00.01-02.00 am	11	5.5
2. 02.01-04.00 am	7	3.5
3. 04.01-06.00 am	4	2.0
4. 06.01-08.00 am	8	4.0
5. 08.01-10.00 am	18	9.0
6. 10.01-12.00 am	27	13.5
7. 00.01-02.00 pm	36	18.0
8. 02.01-04.00 pm	29	14.5
9. 04.01-06.00 pm	13	6.5
10. 06.01-08.00 pm	21	10.5
11. 08.01-10.00 pm	15	7.5
12. 10.01-12.00 pm	11	5.5
Total	200	100.0

Table V shows that on holiday during 12.01-14.00 hrs. and during 14.01-16.00 hrs are the two periods of time that most students listen to the radio which cover 18.0% and 14.5% of the total respondents respectively.

Part B. Satisfaction of University Students on the Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University Radio Station

Data analysis of students' satisfaction towards Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University radio broadcast consists of 3 aspects, which are place for listening service, quality of signal, and contents which are presented in Table VI.

Students are highly satisfied with 'place of listening service', at the mean of 3.9518. With each item considered, it is found that the item with the highest mean is 'sufficiency of listening service points', equal to 3.8805, followed by 'convenience of listening service points' and 'listening effectiveness at listening service points', equal to 3.8636 and 3.4725, respectively.

Students are highly satisfied with 'quality of signal' in general, at the mean of 4.0220. With each item considered, it is found that the item with the highest mean is 'clarity of signal', equal to 3.9587, followed by 'quality of digital signal' and 'quality of analog signal', equal to 3.9091 and 3.7686, respectively.

Students have low satisfaction with contents in general, at the mean of 2.6935. With each item considered, it is found that the item with the average mean is 'matching contents with students' need', equal to 3.4755. In this regard, students

request for more contents in entertainment and sports programs.

TABLE VI
SATISFACTION OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS ON THE SUAN SUNANDHA RAJABHAT UNIVERSITY RADIO STATION

Place of Listening Service in General	3.9518	.5689	High
1. Sufficiency of Listening Service Points	3.8802	.6296	High 1
2. Convenience of Listening Service Points	3.8636	.6832	High 2
3. Listening Effectiveness	3.4752	1.0028	Average 3
Quality of Signal in General	4.0220	.6008	High
4. Clarity of Signal	3.9587	.6805	High 1
5. Quality of Digital Signal	3.9091	.6377	High 2
6. Quality of Analog Signal	3.7686	.7486	High 3
Content	2.6935	.9238	Low
7. Matching Contents with Students' Need	3.4755	.9032	Average 1
8. Interest of Contents	2.4653	.9094	Low 2
9. Variety of Contents	2.5777	.9806	Low 3

V. CONCLUSIONS

A. General Information: Gender, Age, College Year, Faculty

The study finds that most students from the sample group are female between 17–20 years old, third year students from Faculty of Management and Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences.

B. Students Satisfaction of the Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University Radio Station

From the study of data analysis of students' satisfaction in various aspects, which are place of listening service, quality of signal, contents.

Students are highly satisfied with place of listening service. With each item considered, it is found that the item with the highest mean is sufficiency of listening service points, followed by "convenience of listening service points" and "listening effectiveness at listening service points", respectively [5].

Students are highly satisfied with quality of signal in general. with each item considered, it is found that the item with the highest mean is clarity of signal, followed by "quality of digital signal" and "quality of analog signal", respectively.

Students have low satisfaction with contents. They find that contents are not interesting, with low variety, and request for more contents in entertainment and sports programs.

VI. SUGGESTION

From this research, although students are satisfied with Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University radio broadcast, to increase their satisfaction, the management of the University should give precedence and improve all aspects to enhance satisfaction and efficiency of students' learning in the future; i.e. increase of content variety, up-to-date contents, to match students' need, by inserting knowledge into entertainment program for students who can be simultaneously entertained and educated. In addition, there should be more channels to listen to the University radio broadcast for students; i.e. listening via application on mobile phone or tablet.

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